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The Epinephrine Potentiating Effect of Sodium Ascorbate in Allergy

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The striking success of antihistaminic agents such as pyribenzamine, benadryl and several others in controlling the nasal turgescence and rhinorrhea of seasonal hay fever, and in relieving the symptoms of urticaria, led to exaggerated hopes of similar results in the treatment of asthma. While the effectiveness of antihistaminic agents has lent considerable support to the role of histamine in allergy, it may also tend to overemphasize the histamine side.

In asthma pyribenzamine apparently fails to dilate the bronchioles thus giving little or no comfort to the patient. This would suggest that normal bronchiolar tone is the result of an active balance between the constricting action of histamine and the dilating capacity of epinephrin.

In a previous publication I¹ described the experimental microscopic observation of bronchiolar reaction to histamine and the antihistamine effect of Vitamin C. In this experiment the lung of the white New Zealand rabbit was filled with gelatin and then excised and kept viable in Ringer-Locke-Glucose solution. After chilling, the lung was cut so that each section contained a bron-

chiole. This was mounted on a small ring so that it could be observed under the microscope. The gelatin was now washed out of the lung tissue and the whole preparation was maintained viable in the Ringer-Locke-Glucose solution at a fixed temperature. When histamine was added to the solution, the bronchiole promptly contracted and the change of size was drawn through the camera lucida and calculated by means of the planimeter. After the addition of Vitamin C, the bronchiole recovered from the contractions and became moderately dilated. If epinephrine was added the dilatation would increase further. [For the exact technique reference may be made to the original article.]

At the time of the reporting of this experiment I interpreted the dilatation of the bronchiole after the histamine contraction as attributable to the antihistamine action of Vitamin C. In the light of subsequent study I am inclined to believe that the counteraction of the histamine contraction was due, not to the chemical neutralization of histamine, but rather to the potentiation of the epinephrin already present in the viable section of bronchiole. This explanation became even more probable from the demonstration that, if additional epinephrin was added, the bronchiole dilated to twice the size of the normal bronchiole before the histamine had been added, thus showing that a very active dilator effect was produced.

As one followed this hypothesis it seemed important to study every possible avenue for potentiating the body reserves of epinephrine present in the tissues of the asthmatic. In this investigation it became apparent that the whole suprarenal mechanism was involved in an intimate relationship with Vitamin C and Sodium. The clinical administration of sodium ascorbate was uniquely effective.

In practical application it was possible to demonstrate that daily dosages between 1000 mg. to 2000 mg. of Vitamin C afforded many patients considerable relief from allergic manifestations and some even striking and dramatic improvement. There remained, however, a group of patients that was either not benefited or only moderately improved.

Analysis of these latter patients showed, as a rule, concomitant infection with a history of repeated colds or bronchial infections. They were of the type usually classified as persons with a lowered resistance to infection.

When, as a result of technical advance in Vitamin C research by the author, there was made commercially available the dry sodium salt of Vitamin C, an investigation of its use in allergy was undertaken. Originally, it was believed that the chief advantage of the sodium salt would be in the fact that it was a neutral form of Vitamin C. Since the high dosage of Vitamin C entailed a daily amount of 1.5 grams to 2 grams, gastric irritation was experienced frequently. Another factor was the continued, and, at times, undesirable increase in ingested acid.

While the kidney has the power to form ammonia for the purpose of neutralizing an acid urine, it may also produce acid as NaH_2PO_4 as well as free organic acid, provided the pH does not fall much lower than 4.0. When, however, large amounts of acid are introduced into or produced in the body, the ammonia producing mechanism of the kidney cannot suffice and the sodium bicarbonate of the blood is depleted for the purpose of neutralizing the acid. The CO_2 is exhaled by the lungs and the sodium salt of the acid appears in the urine; hydrochloric acid, for example, is excreted as sodium chloride, sulphuric acid as sodium sulphate.

If acid be fed and base is withheld from the diet for some days, sodium salts are excreted at first and a little extra potassium, calcium or magnesium appears. Gradually, as the requirement for base becomes more insistent, abnormally large amounts of potassium are excreted. The body manifestly resists potassium loss as long as possible; probably because potassium and magnesium are essential to cell function in a more direct way than sodium. The depression of sodium levels may play an important role in kidney blockage from drugs of the sulfa group. Thus the availability of sodium ascorbate gave us an important agent in acid base equilibrium.

Analysis of blood and tissues shows a remarkable difference in distribution of cations—according to Holmes.²

Cation	Milligrams in 100 grams of plasma	Milligrams in 100 grams of muscle
Sodium	138.0	60.0
Potassium	18.0	360.0
Calcium	10.5	10.0
Magnesium	2.7	23.0

It is apparent that tissue cells contain far more potassium than sodium and that sodium loss would come first. Sodium, however plays a vital role in connection with the normal metabolism of the adrenal cortex. One could consider that the adrenal cortical hormone, sodium and Vitamin C bear a reciprocal relationship to each other. It is, therefore, not surprising to find that the cortical hormone protected against histamine shock just as Vitamin C does. Thus Ingle³ showed the protective effect of fragments of viable cortical tissue and of transplants of cortical tissue on the resistance of suprarenalectomized rats to histamine shock. These observations were confirmed by Wyman⁴ and Turn Suden.⁵ They also showed that the increased susceptibility of the rat to histamine after suprarenalectomy depends on the loss both of medullary and cortical function. In an earlier paper on Histamine-Adrenalin Balance in Allergy I¹ pointed out that shock of the most varied sort ranging from severe burns and trauma to poisonings have a common histamine reaction directly analogous to nasal allergy and asthma.

The interrelationship of the adrenal cortical hormone to Vitamin C and Sodium led to the

hypothesis that this triad of substances may play a basic role in allergy and that the deficiency of any one or more of these elements would predispose to allergic reactions. The Pottengers⁶ had already treated a group of 50 allergic children suffering with asthma by means of whole adrenal gland and a high salt intake. In addition a diet rich in vitamins and minerals was given. Improvement was observed in 84 per cent of the patients.

It now remained to observe the isolated effect of sodium ascorbate. Marine & Baumann⁷ had found that daily intraperitoneal injections of various sodium salts such as isotonic sodium chloride, sodium acetate, Ringers Solution, prolonged the lives of suprarenalectomized controls. They pointed out the specific value of sodium salts in maintaining the life of the animal. Similar findings were observed by Stewart and Rogoff,⁸ although they found that salt solution could not be used as a substitute for cortical hormone. Loeb and his co-workers⁹ extended the studies and from their work suggested that suprarenal insufficiency was associated with a primary loss of sodium through the kidney. Harrop and his associates¹⁰ were able to maintain bilaterally suprarenalectomized dogs for as long a period as five months without the use of any suprarenal gland preparation or extract by the administration of sodium chloride and sodium bicarbonate alone. Withdrawal of the salt then produced typical suprarenal insufficiency. It has been shown by Zwemer and Truszkowski¹¹ that a drop in sodium concentration in the blood is associated with a significant rise in the Potassium concentration. The production of such an electrolyte disturbance, as suggested by Gilman and Yannet,¹² decreases the natural resistance of unoperated rats to histamine poisoning (Perla and Sandberg¹³).

However, Perla and Marmorstan¹⁴ found that, when cortin is administered during the early period of insufficiency, the resistance of suprarenalectomized animals is raised to a striking degree, whereas when epinephrin is similarly administered, the resistance is raised only to a slight degree. By the administration of cortin, they were able to raise the resistance of suprarenalectomized

rats to histamine almost to the normal level. A further interesting point arose when the cortical hormone was used in experimental infections. Scott, Bradford, Hartman and McCoy¹⁵ determined the effect of the cortical hormone on the resistance of normal animals. Three types of intoxication were used; diphtheria toxin in the guinea pig, trypanosome equiperdum infection in the rat and pneumococcus infection in the mouse. No protection was obtained against one minimum lethal dose, of toxin by administration of cortical extract in amounts of one and one half cc. Injections of cortin were begun after the injection of diphtheria toxin. Similar results were produced in the other infections. All the mice were dead within 32 hours. The administration of cortical extract did not produce any appreciable survival period of white mice following infection with pneumococcus.

Zemmer & Jungeblut¹⁶ demonstrated some protection by the injection of cortical extract in normal guinea pigs against a minimum lethal dose of diphtheria toxin. On the whole the results were not striking, although apparently, under certain conditions, the administration of a large dose of a cortical extract may protect the guinea pig against more than one M.L.D. of diphtheria toxin.

Thaddea,¹⁷ however, observed definitely beneficial effects of injection of cortical hormone when combined with Vitamin C on the resistance of guinea pigs to diphtheria. Cosentino,¹⁸ likewise, reported favorable results in rabbits infected intraperitoneally with cultures of staphylococcus aureus by the use of Vitamin C and adrenal cortical hormone.

Heuer and Andrus¹⁹ have reported that cortical extract has a protective action against the shock produced by intravenous injection of intestinal loop fluid into dogs. Meek²⁰ also noted beneficial effects from the administration of cortin to dogs suffering from shock following intestinal distension. There is the further observation of Wolfram and Zwemer²¹ in the amelioration of anaphylactic shock in guinea pigs by the prior administration of cortin.

The interrelationship of histamine sensi-

tivity to adrenal cortical insufficiency and sodium and Vitamin C led to the hypothesis that nasal allergy and asthma may be precipitated by an imbalance of the triad cortical hormone-Sodium-Vitamin C. In view of the reciprocal capacity that exists between them, a study was undertaken on the effect of so-

dium ascorbate, particularly in those allergic patients who were somewhat refractory to high dosage ascorbic acid. The beneficial effects were strikingly greater than ascorbic acid itself. There was, in addition, marked freedom from gastric irritation with the use of 2 grams daily. Increased diuresis was

Name	Age	Sex	History	Treatment and Results
1. E. H.	64	F.	Sneezing for about 2 years, in summer and early spring. Some asthmatic attacks during this time. Some food allergies. Nasal passage always feels congested.	4/21—Started taking sodium ascorbate tablets 3 t.i.d. Sneezing at this time. 4/28—Relieved completely by sodium ascorbate tablets of sneezing. No congestion of nose, continued taking 3 t.i.d. 5/24—Relieved completely of all symptoms, no congestion of nose. Mucosa normal, no irritation of stomach. Slight increase of urine during 1st 2 weeks, the following week no increase due to taking of aspirin for extraction of tooth. Now taking 1 sodium ascorbate tablet t.i.d.
2. B. W.	25	F.	Hay fever for past 15 years. More severe last two seasons. Unable to work during hay fever season.	Allergic testing 4+ reaction to ragweed and timothy. Started hay fever injections 5/12/45. Given 1 every 5 days. Taking sodium ascorbate pills, 2 t.i.d. Series of injections finished 7/2/45. Patient not seen again at office. Mother reports that patient had a very good summer. Very little sneezing and running of nose. No stomach irritation. Considers this the best summer she has had for a number of years.
3. L. G.	45	M.	Sneezing from March 20 to May 14 every year. Has nose bleed during sneezing attacks. Allergic testing shows no sensitivity to scratch tests. Itching of eyes and nose also at this time.	Allergy testing for spring grasses and trees shows no specific reaction. Given special spring tree vaccine, starting 12/18/44. First symptoms of spring grass fever on 3/5/45. Started sodium ascorbate pills, 1 t.i.d. On 3/26/45 given 2 sodium ascorbate pills, t.i.d.* Slept the first time in 2 weeks. 3/27 taking 3 sodium ascorbate pills, t.i.d. On 3/28 patient states that he feels like an entirely different person with very little sneezing after taking the sodium ascorbate tablets. 4/14 patient reports very little sneezing, 40 oz. urine excreted in 24 hours. 4/18 no sneezing, no running of nose for last 2 weeks. Sleeps well, feeling excellent. 4/25 nose congested. Patient without sodium ascorbate pills for one week. Sneezing some. Given sodium ascorbate pills, 2 t.i.d. 5/2 nose not congested. No sneezing, no running.
4. R. B.	30	M.	Hay fever and asthma for 20 years, 44- reaction to dust, feathers, ragweed and timothy.	Started hay fever injections 5/14/45 combined with sodium ascorbate tablets, 3 t.i.d. Given hay fever injections twice weekly. Patient seen at office after Sept. 1 and stated that so far he has had the best season. After June 15, he took 2 sodium ascorbate tablets, t.i.d. Very little sneezing. No irritation of stomach or increase of urination.
5. J. C.	22	F.	Hay fever for about 8-10 years. Suffers from asthmatic attacks during hay fever season. An uncle died of asthma.	Allergy testing showed 4+ to dust, ragweed and timothy. Allergic to foods as well. Given adrenalin injection to control hives and itching after testing for ragweed and timothy. Eyes swollen also. Started hay fever injections 5/7/45. Given 1 injection every 5 days. Started sodium ascorbate tablets, 3 t.i.d., at the same time as hay fever injections. Finished hay fever injections 6/28/45, completing series. At this time she was taking 2 sodium ascorbate tablets, t.i.d. Patient seen again 9/6/45, stating that at that time she had been entirely free of sneezing up to this time. Sneezing and symptoms usually worse from the end of Aug. to Sept. 15. Seen again 9/11 and 9/15. No symptoms at all at this time. No irritation of stomach, no increase of urination or diarrhea during the time the tablets were taken. Patient states that this is the first season she has been entirely free of any hay fever symptoms. No asthmatic attacks during season.
6. B. B.	16	F.	Hay fever for 2 years. Sneezing and running nose. Sneezing starting in July through middle of August. No food allergies.	4+ reaction to ragweed and timothy. Started sodium ascorbate tablets, 1 t.i.d. on 6/13/44. Increased to 2 t.i.d., 7/1/45. No sneezing or running of nose at present. Patient returned to office 9/11/45. At that time patient stated that she went without pills one day and her nose started to run immediately. After taking 2 sodium ascorbate tablets nose stopped almost instantly. Slight heartburn at times. May be due to sodium ascorbate tablets. No increase of urination.

Name	Age	Sex	History	Treatment and Results
7. S. R.	35	F.	Sneezing and running nose for last year with no relief. Hay fever for 17 years. Asthmatic attacks in hay fever season.	Allergy testing shows 4+ reaction to dust, ragweed and timothy, also allergic to some foods. Started hay fever injections 5/7/45. Given 1 injection every 5 days. Started sodium ascorbate pills, 3 t.i.d., at same time. Finished series of hay fever injections 6/28/45. Now taking sodium ascorbate tablets, 2 t.i.d. Patient seen again each week from 9/6/45 to 10/19/45. During this time patient reports entire relief from all symptoms of hay fever that she suffered during previous years. Has had no asthmatic attacks during the season. No irritation of stomach, slight increase in urination, no diarrhea. Sneezing and running of nose entirely cleared. Patient considers this the best season she has had for some time.
8. P. S.	45	M.	Hay fever for last 7 years, asthmatic attacks at times. No food allergies.	Allergy testing: 4+ to ragweed and timothy. Started hay fever injections 5/3/45. Started sodium ascorbate tablets, 2 t.i.d., at the same time. Given injections every 5 days. Series of injections ending 6/29/45. Continuing to take sodium ascorbate tablets, 2 t.i.d. Returned to office 10/13/45. At this time patient states that he has had a much better season than previously. This is the first season that he has not had any asthmatic attacks. Very little sneezing. No irritation of stomach or increase in urination.
9- F. S.	27	F.	Hay fever for last 8 years. Nasal stuffiness, sneezing, and running. Had 6 injections of hydrochloric acid for hay fever without results. No asthmatic attacks. No known food allergies.	Allergic testing 4+ to timothy and ragweed. Started hay fever injections 5/10/45. Started sodium ascorbate, 2 t.i.d., at the same time. Series of injections finished 6/28/45. Patient visited office 9/3/45. Has had first hay fever symptom, but very little sneezing. Increased sodium ascorbate tablets to 3 t.i.d. 9/15 patient reports very little sneezing. Feeling better this year than at any previous time. No irritation of stomach, no increase of urination. 8/15/45 started sodium ascorbate tablets, 2 t.i.d. Gastric upset after taking 2 t.i.d. for 2 days. 8/22/45 gastric upset, started taking 1 t.i.d. 9/4/45—No sneezing this season. Patient reports the best season since she can remember. During this season patient also took hay fever injections from local physician.
10. L. G.	25	F.	History of hay fever in August since childhood.	Allergy testing shows child to be allergic to ragweed and timothy, also to most foods. 6/17/45—Started sodium ascorbate pills, 1 t.i.d. Continued with no sneezing or hives through entire hay fever season. Last season patient started on C.B. pills, 1 t.i.d., which caused upset stomach. Patient was then given nucleic acid with some relief but not as dramatic as the sodium ascorbate pills.
11. R. R.	6	M.	Had hives at age of 3 with spots on chest. No nasal symptoms. At 4 developed sneezing and rhinitis in August and September.	5/24/45—Started ragweed injections 1 every 5. Also started taking sodium ascorbate tablets, 2 t.i.d. 6/15/45—Taking sodium ascorbate tablets, 3 t.i.d. No gastric disturbances. 6/27/45—Finished hay fever series. 9/10/45—Patient reported at office stating that attacks have been lessened this summer. When patient had an occasional severe attack accompanied by asthmatic attack, she took 3 sodium ascorbate tablets and attack was greatly relieved.
12. N. H.	25	F.	Has had hay fever for the last 4 years, complicated by asthma the last 2 years. Allergy tests 3 years ago shows sensitivity to dust, ragweed and timothy.	5/18/45—Started hay fever series 1 every 5 days. Also started sodium ascorbate pills, 3 t.i.d. 6/30/45—Slight digestive disturbance. Reduced dosage 2 t.i.d. 9/5/45—Patient seen at office. Reports very little sneezing. Usually at this time patient suffers with hay fever. Mostly from 9/1 to 9/10. Taking 2 t.i.d. 9/12/45—Patient states that he had no sneezing at all this season.
13. W. L.	46	M.	Hay fever for 30 years with asthmatic attacks.	

noted almost as a rule. Several of the patients were intractable asthmatics who had been refractory to almost all forms of therapy, but these patients have remained free from asthma in a fairly continuous level of sodium ascorbate. The seasonal hay fever patients did particularly well.

In reviewing the results obtained with ascorbic acid, calcium ascorbate, and sodium

ascorbate, it would appear that the inorganic ion plays a very important role. It is not improbable that many factors influence histamine sensitivity. Among these are enzymatic reactions and toxic factors that are favorably influenced by calcium ion, whereas another important group may be strikingly helped by the sodium ion. In both instances the inorganic ion, as the salt of ascorbic

acid, represents a very desirable form of the therapy in allergy.

The use of the sodium salt of ascorbic acid may also play an important role in other conditions such as urinary lithiasis, when the solvent action of the ascorbate on carbonates is utilized, as well as the solubilizing effect of the sodium ion.

While the desirability of a sodium salt of ascorbic acid was obvious, great technical obstacles presented themselves. There was no dry sodium salt of ascorbic acid available. The instability of ascorbic acid in alkali solution was well known and described in virtually every test dealing with ascorbic acid. In fact Sherman²² points out the ready destruction of ascorbic acid by alkali, and the Merck Index also describes the same. When ascorbic acid decomposes, it goes to oxalic acid with its strong tendency to deplete the calcium ion. An unstable sodium salt of ascorbic acid would thus be less desirable than ascorbic acid itself. Karrer²³ had tried to prepare a sodium salt of ascorbic acid by reacting sodium ethylate in ethyl alcohol but found the procedure tricky and uncertain with a strong tendency to decomposition. It thus appeared that the preparation of a stable salt of sodium ascorbate was doomed to failure. Many different attempts to secure this valuable product were made unsuccessfully until one day the reaction was run between sodium methylate and ascorbic acid in methyl alcohol. This yielded a remarkably stable sodium ascorbate that was even more stable than Vitamin C itself and resisted heat in the oven for over 500 hours assuring freedom from such decomposition products as oxalic acid.

The explanation of this phenomenon led to much chemical speculation as to whether the sodium ion reacts with the hydroxyl in the second or third carbon atom, since the ring is not considered broken in the formation of the salt. Study of the reaction conducted by Karrer,²³ and compared to that which I carried out, showed a marked difference in the character of the crystallization which is apparently responsible for the differences in degree of stability. Thanks to the availability of the pure product the clinical investigation could be conducted.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The availability of the sodium salt of the ascorbic acid for oral use represents a marked advance in the therapeutic approach to allergy.
2. The increased sensitivity to histamine in suprarenalectomized animals suggests a relationship between adrenal cortical hormone-sodium-Vitamin C and allergy.
3. In refractory cases of allergy and asthma, sodium ascorbate was more effective than ascorbic acid.

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